
A SOFTWARE DESIGN PHILOSOPHY

Software Design as a Practice of Thinking

Omer Gindi

2025

Table of Contents

INTRODUCTION	3
<i>OPENING WORDS</i>	4
UNDERSTANDING THE LANDSCAPE	5
<i>BASICS OF SOFTWARE DESIGN</i>	6
<i>CHALLENGES</i>	7
UNDERLYING DESIGN PRINCIPLES	8
<i>DEPENDENCIES</i>	9
<i>OWNERSHIP OF RESOURCES</i>	13
<i>SECURITY FROM THE GROUND UP</i>	15
<i>DESIGNING FOR CHANGE</i>	19
<i>HANDLING COMPLEXITY</i>	22
<i>DEALING WITH UNCERTAINTY</i>	23
<i>BALANCE</i>	25
HUMAN FACTORS IN DESIGN	26
<i>DESIGN'S ROLE IN ENABLING EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION</i>	27
<i>MULTI-TEAM SYSTEMS</i>	32
HOW I DESIGN	33
<i>MY DESIGN APPROACH</i>	34
<i>SAYINGS</i>	35
HOW DESIGN AFFECTS CODE QUALITY	36
<i>CLEAN CODE</i>	37

REFACTORING..... 39

ESTABLISHED DESIGN METHODOLOGIES..... **40**

DOMAIN DRIVEN DESIGN..... 41

EVENT SOURCING..... 45

CLUES WITHIN DESIGN..... **48**

DESIGN SMELLS..... 49

General..... 49

Abstraction..... 50

Ease of Change..... 50

EMERGING TOOLS..... **54**

AI IN SOFTWARE DESIGN..... 55

DESIGN AS A SERIES OF TRADEOFFS..... **58**

INSIDE OUT OR OUTSIDE IN?..... 59

TRADEOFFS..... 60

CLOSING REMARKS..... **61**

FAREWELL WORDS..... 62

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL..... **63**

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS..... 64

TABLE OF FIGURES..... 65

REFERENCES AND ADDITIONAL READING..... 66

APPENDICES..... 67

Appendix A: Technical Glossary..... 67

Introduction

Chapter 1

Sections:

- *Opening Words*

Overview:

This chapter provides the opening words and frames the purpose of the paper.

Opening Words

Software design is less about formulas and more about critical thinking. Unlike coding or debugging, it does not offer definitive answers or standardized solutions. Each project presents unique challenges and trade offs that demand careful consideration. Therefore, understanding *how* to think critically about design - asking the right questions and making deliberate decisions - is far more valuable than simply memorizing rules or applying patterns mechanically.

Design is fundamentally an art rather than a science. There is no absolute right or wrong, nor a “perfect” design. Instead, the goal is to strive for the best possible balance of trade-offs suited to the system’s unique needs.

While numerous tools exist, including SOLID, component design, UMLs, design patterns, DRY, IoC, N-tier architecture, microservices, monoliths, and more, these are not tools in the traditional sense. Unlike a Git branch or a decompiler in IDA, they don't do the work for you. Rather, they serve as guidelines meant to make you think about important aspects in your design and to facilitate communication among architects. This paper also aims to help you understand what lies beyond these tools, the underlying principles and concepts like dependencies and ownership, and why they matter, so that software design tools serve as reminders to guide your thinking rather than rigid rules to follow.

These tools and patterns offer valuable perspectives but simply replicating them without adapting or modifying to fit your context limits your design's effectiveness and cohesion. A better approach is to understand the principles behind the tools and thoughtfully shape them for each unique situation.

True system design arises from asking the right questions and seeking thoughtful answers. This paper explores the mindset behind design and offers ways to cultivate a thoughtful approach to challenges such as dealing with uncertainty, evolving requirements, and balancing trade offs, fostering adaptability and resilience without prescribing fixed solutions.

Understanding The Landscape

Chapter 2

Sections:

- *Basics of Software Design*
- *Challenges*

Overview:

This section covers the necessary background required for the rest of the paper.

Basics of Software Design

Before we begin, it's worth outlining why we design software, how we approach it, and what benefits it brings before rushing to implementation.

Software systems are often large and complex, making them hard to build as one block and more prone to bugs caused by tangled dependencies, uncontrolled resource access, and other pitfalls. Software design is the process of deciding how to break a system into smaller, well-defined responsibilities, how those parts communicate, and how they use shared services and resources-while ensuring all requirements are met. For example, a chat app might have separate components like “ChatWindow” and “BackupUploader”. With careful design, we could make group and private chats work independently by using abstractions - definitions of “what” something does without deciding “how” it does it yet. For instance, we could define an interface “ILogger” with a single method “void log (const char[] message)”. This lets us create different implementations like “FileLogger” and “ConsoleLogger” while treating them the same way as ILogger instances.

A good design makes a system easier to read, keeps logic where you expect it, allows parts to change without breaking others, and simplifies adding new features. Now we are ready to dive into how to think about design.

Challenges

How do you build a large, complex system in which each part is as isolated as possible - minimizing coupling while maintaining cohesion? Software is bound to change, so how do you create a system that is both flexible and robust, extensible with minimal changes to existing code without breaking anything or pre adding unnecessary complexity? A system that is straightforward and grounded in its requirements, yet flexible and future-proof. These are the challenges we face when designing systems - and the hallmarks of good design: stability with flexibility, futureproofing grounded in real needs, and scale without sacrificing readability.

Underlying Design Principles

Chapter 3

Sections:

- *Dependencies*
- *Ownership of Resources*
- *Security From the Ground Up*
- *Designing for Change*
- *Handling Complexity*
- *Dealing With Uncertainty*
- *Balance*

Overview:

This chapter explores what lies beneath our design tools and aims to foster a deeper perspective on designing systems beyond surface-level rules.

Dependencies

Probably the underlying challenge of all designs is dependencies, firstly let's talk about what is the consequence of A to depend on B:

1. A cannot exist or compile without B.
2. A knows about B and aware of its structure.
3. A is affected when B changes. The practical meaning is that when B changes A might break and require changes as well.

It's just like an electric kettle that is connected to a power outlet. The kettle can't work without it, and it must match the outlet's shape and voltage exactly. If the outlet, or any of its properties, changes then the kettle might stop working, behave inconsistently, or only function partially. In the same way, when one part of a system depends on another, it becomes tightly coupled to its existence and details, making it fragile and harder to change safely.

Now imagine a chain of 100 classes that depend on one another and on external resources (Like DB, libraries). If class B changes. It can create a cascade of changes across the whole system! Which will then create more changes and can introduce bugs and major changes throughout the system, and all because one tiny class changed. It is dangerous!

Solution: ensure high-level modules don't depend on low-level implementations, keep components isolated, and manage both direct and hidden dependencies (i.e., dependencies of your dependencies or implementations hidden behind abstractions) with great care.

Figure 1 - Dependencies Summary

Now, let's see it in practice.

We're in a newsroom, preparing reports for the upcoming show. So, we create a "ShowOrganizer" that collects and arranges reports. These reports are generated by "JournalistWorker", who gathers information from witnesses, instances of the Witness class.

Here's our current diagram:

Figure 2 - Bad Newsroom Class Diagram

Notice the problem? If the Witness class changes, the impact ripples all the way to the show. For example, if a witness has seen multiple events and now wants to share all of them, it might return a list or require a parameter specifying which event to describe. Until the journalist updates their internal implementation to handle the change, the show is blocked.

But this doesn't make sense - witnesses shouldn't dictate how journalists do their job. To decouple them, we introduce an abstraction that all witnesses must implement. This removes the journalist's dependency on specific implementation details.

Here's the updated diagram:

Figure 3 - Good Newsroom Class Diagram

Ownership of Resources

Who owns a resource? Where is it needed? What is its scope? Clear ownership defines responsibility, limits coupling, and helps validate whether component boundaries make sense. While some resources must be shared, we strive to minimize uncontrolled access. When possible, each resource should have a clear owning component - the only place responsible for its lifecycle and modification. Ownership is a key lens for assessing isolation and architectural integrity, not by forbidding sharing, but by making responsibility explicit and defining structural conventional way to access external resources.

Let's consider a library: the books are the resources, and they're arranged in a specific order by the librarian. Visitors can come in, browse the shelves, and borrow the book they want. When it's time to return the book, the librarian places it back in its proper spot, managing the resource, according to a consistent system. This ensures no book gets lost, and it makes it easy to search for specific titles or attributes (e.g., all books written by *Christopher Paolini*).

Now imagine if library members returned books themselves: kids' books would end up in the horror section, people would hide books for later, and everything would descend into chaos.

To avoid this, we must carefully manage and separate our resources. In our better-designed library, the "BorrowingService" handles the borrowing and returning events, keeping the responsibilities of members and books separate. The "InventoryManager" tracks all the books, while the librarian is responsible for maintaining the order of the shelves.

Here is our better designed class diagram:

Figure 4 - Library Class Diagram

Security From the Ground Up

When designing a system, it's important to put an emphasis on security from the ground up. So, let's see what to keep in mind:

1. **Isolation and ownership.** Each component should have access only for the resources it needs, this is called the principle of least privilege. It keeps critical resources masked from most of the system and limits an attacker options if they breach it.
2. **Exposure.** You should minimize attack surfaces, expose only what is truly necessary and hide the real logic behind strong input validation. Never trust a data that has come from the outside, and don't blindly trust data from the inside as well. Which leads up to point 3.
3. **Input validation.** Arguably the best practice in secure coding. Validate and sanitize every input. Use whitelisting, not blacklisting, to limit options (e.g., ensure a number `num` is between 10 and 15 by checking `(num >= 10) && (num <= 15)` and not `!(num < 10) && !(num > 15)`) because this way the default behaviour for an unthought edge case is to block rather than allow, preventing many security risks.
4. **Limit error information leakage.** Errors that return to the user are valuable to attackers. They expose information that seem naive but is actually very helpful. For example, if a there is a username and password input and the error is or “User does not exist” or “Password is incorrect” if an attacker enters the

username “admin” and the error returned is that “Password is incorrect” the attacker gains the knowledge that there is in fact a user named “admin”.

5. **Audit and logging.** It is generally a good practice to have a logging infrastructure as it is a strong tool to debug, usage analysis and catch unusual events. But for security it is critical. Logging allows us to spot an attacker, helps us recover from a security breach, and identify points of failure within the system.

Here is a basic security architecture for accessing resources:

Figure 5 - Secured Resource Access System Class Diagram

And here is the non-secure version:

Figure 6 - Straightforward Resource Access System Class Diagram

If you look at these diagrams and think security adds a lot of overhead - you're right. But in today's world, designing your system with security in mind from the ground up is invaluable. It's not just about avoiding breaches; it's about building resilient, trustworthy, and future-proof systems. The added complexity is a small price to pay for protecting your users, data, and infrastructure. Teams like the SOC and NOC are there to support this foundation - detecting, monitoring, and responding to threats - but without designing for security and implementing logs, access controls, and other protective measures, even the best response teams won't be able to defend effectively.

DESIGN FOR SECURITY

Emphasize security from the ground up, keeping in mind:

Isolation and Ownership

Each component should have access only to the resources it needs

Exposure

Minimize attack surfaces, validate inputs, expose only what is necessary

Input Validation

Validate and sanitize every input

Limit Error Information Leakage

Avoid revealing sensitive information in errors

Audit and Logging

Record security-relevant activity within the system

Generated by DALL-E
for Omer Gindi

Figure 7 - Design For Security Summary

Designing for Change

Design is for making changes easy more than getting everything right at the start. There are going to be more features, the system is going to grow. How do we make the evolution as easy, quick and well architected? We design for change.

We organize the code into loosely coupled modules, so changes and additions stay local and don't ripple across the whole system. We intentionally leave room for future changes. When we identify a likely future need, we enable it structurally - without building it fully.

Imagine a house with a basement that might one day become a rental apartment. Right now, it's just a basement, so there's no need for a full kitchen or a separate entrance. But the architect prepares for the possibility: water and electricity are already wired in, the basement is separated from the rest of the house by a single door, and there's an outside path running alongside its wall. No wall is cut for a door yet, and no kitchen is built. Later, if the owner decides to convert it, all that's needed to do is to block the connecting door, add the kitchen, and open an external door. That's far easier than retrofitting plumbing, rewiring the house, or creating an access path after construction. The structural provisions were made early—when it was simple to do so—but the actual apartment was built only when it was needed.

For example: suppose we design a building with one apartment per floor. If we anticipate that one day a floor might hold multiple apartments, we don't implement that logic yet, but we use an abstraction to make it easy to support both cases in the future. We define an interface like "IStorePeople" with a method `getPeopleAmount()`. In the current single-apartment case, this simply returns `apartment.getPeopleAmount()`.

Later, if we support multiple apartments, we can create another implementation that sums over all apartments - without touching the original code.

Figure 8 - Single/Multi Apartment Class Diagram

We also use dependency injection (DI), factories, and external configuration to make the system behaviour configurable. With DI, we inject abstractions, so we can swap behaviours without touching internal code. This preserves backward compatibility and allows new features to plug into the same interface. Using configurations and factories also helps us prevent changes in the code and makes the additions for the system to be only from the outside and to be easily interchangeable - aligning with the Open/Closed Principle: open for extension, closed for modification.

DESIGN FOR CHANGE

Organize code into loosely coupled modules, leaving room for future changes.

Generated by DALL-E
for Omer Gindi

Figure 9 - Design for Change Summary

Handling Complexity

Of course, sometimes we find ourselves in messy situations. It's important to recognize when the part you're designing becomes overly complex and full of patches just to meet all its requirements. When that happens, you should stop. Rethink the design with your new understanding of the requirements.

Most of the time, you'll find a simpler and more efficient solution.

Think about the last time you packed a suitcase. You probably started with a list. But halfway through, you remembered you also needed slippers for the pool, suncream, and long jeans for the evening restaurant. So, you tossed those items on top and tried to close the suitcase - only to find it wouldn't shut.

What do you do then? You stop forcing it. You unpack everything, empty the suitcase, and start again - this time arranging all the items thoughtfully, considering each one's size and shape. You take a complex problem ("How do I fit these slippers into this tiny space?") and rethink your approach so everything fits.

Dealing with Uncertainty

This is a tough one, how do you design something when you don't fully understand it yet? The key is to focus on three core principles: Document, Change, Isolation.

1. **Document** every assumption, decision, and rationale. Unlike routine design steps, these choices aren't obvious or standard - they're more fragile, and more likely to evolve. Clear documentation is essential for future you and for other architects who will revisit or extend this design.
2. **Design for Change** by making the uncertain parts as flexible and replaceable as possible. You lack the domain knowledge to predict how this component will evolve, so your best bet is adaptability. Avoid locking into rigid structures too early.
3. **Isolate** the unknown. Encapsulate it behind well-defined interfaces and limit its exposure across the system. When change comes, and it will, it should affect only a small, localized area, not ripple through the whole architecture.

Let's look at a smart farm management system.

Our farm uses weather services to determinate planting times and irrigation needs for the crops, but how we analyse the weather is not decided yet. We have not chosen a weather API, and we haven't created the algorithms yet. So, what do we do? We hide the weather analysis and data behind an interface that processes the weather and returns an action to perform. We isolate the weather provider so that only the analysers will access it and make both the analysers and the weather provider interchangeable.

Figure 10 - Smart Farm Management System Class Diagram

Finally, defer decisions when possible. Use simplicity and abstraction to keep your options open until you gain more clarity.

Balance

It's important to recognize the recurring theme of balance. On one hand, we want to engineer everything to make the system clean and correct. On the other, overengineering is harmful - unnecessary complexity increases development time and, ironically, makes the system harder to maintain and extend. Too many abstractions and excessive separation create flows that are hard to trace. Developers often don't know where the logic happens, making debugging difficult and expanding functionality a logistical nightmare.

Human Factors in Design

Chapter 4

Sections:

- *Design's Role in Enabling Effective Communication*
- *Multi-Team Systems*

Overview:

This chapter views how design affect human's behaviour and how to design for efficient work.

Design's Role in Enabling Effective Communication

Let's think about that for a second. What is the use of an Entity Relationship Diagram? Or a components diagram? Or a class diagram? Or any sort of documentation or diagram? There isn't a single practical use. Those beautiful diagrams we create does not contribute a single thing to the system - they aren't code, and they aren't documentation for users. Their main contribution is communication between people - both communication with future you and with other developers. That's how we transfer ideas, that's how we don't forget, and that's how we train new team members on our systems. Think of it like the children's game “Telephone” (also called “Chinese Whispers”): without documentation and diagrams, we would have to pass knowledge person to person, which might work at first but quickly becomes impossible as the system grows. It would take too much time to explain everything, it wouldn't be possible to remember it all, and data would get lost in the process. This would create technical debt at a scale we haven't seen. Whole parts of the system's rationale and knowledge would be lost.

So now that we understand the importance of software design for developer communication, let's see what we can do to make that communication as clear and effective as possible:

1. **Use meaningful naming.** It's surprising how often I come across classes with names so vague that it's hard to tell what they do. Naming is one of the most important aspects of clean code. Code is written for humans to read, and we

only have a few words to convey intent - so every word counts. Names should be clear, concise, and directly reflect purpose. When a class name includes terms like “Manager” or “Helper”, it's often a sign that it's taking on too many responsibilities. Think about a class named UserManager: does it create and delete users? Handle sessions? Give orders to users? The name is broad enough to mean all of these, which makes it easy for unrelated logic to end up in the same place. For instance, does it make sense for UserManager to contain authenticateUser? Sure - it manages users. What about calculateUserSalary? That too could fit, if the class is tracking employment. But combining both functions in the same place leads to a mix of unrelated concerns. Instead, try naming classes around specific responsibilities: UserAuthenticator for authentication, UserRepository for storage, and UserSalaryCalculator for salary logic. This approach makes each class easier to understand, less likely to be misused, and better structured overall.

2. **Follow conventions.** Conventions are there for a reason - they are our universal language for communicating.
3. **Be consistent.** A codebase should feel like it was written by a single developer. If, in one component, all interfaces are under the folder Abstract but in another they are inside NonLogic/Interfaces, a developer will get confused navigating between them and may introduce messy code parts due to

conflicting styles. Look at this file tree for example:

Figure 11 - Inconsistent File Tree

Let's break down some of the main issues in this file tree:

- There's an “Abstracts” folder in the root directory, but also an “Abstrect” folder inside “Services” - conflicting names, a typo, and two completely different styles of file tree management.

- Naming conventions are all over the place: some use PascalCase, others camelCase or snake_case, and a few are ALL_CAPS.
 - Folder names flip between singular (“Infrastructure”, “Logic”) and plural (“Helpers”, “Services”) with no consistency.
 - Not a problem per se, but relevant to using conventions - naming the folder “Constants” instead of the more common “Consts”. “Constants” is technically correct, but “Consts” is more widely used and carries clearer intent.
4. **Keep components small and focused.** A component that does a single, bounded job is easier to understand than one responsible for many different operations. It’s like a course focused solely on the stock market versus a course covering stocks, real estate, currency, and international transport. In a diverse and complicated course, finding the chapter on the S&P 500 and understanding its relation to the rest is a burden. Likewise, a small component with a clear responsibility is easier to locate, understand, and evolve.
 5. **Keep a text document next to your diagram.** A document that explains your thinking and rationale behind your design choices, describes the evolution of the system over the years, and gives contextual background on the diagram and system. How else would a developer know you chose async over parallelism because the system runs on a single-core, single-thread embedded device?
 6. **Use diagrams, not only text.** Visual representations are generally more effective than the written word for the average human.

Figure 12 - Communication Summary

Multi-Team Systems

Systems developed by multiple teams must have clear boundaries and defined interaction points between team responsibilities. Isolation is key - any time a developer is blocked waiting on someone else's work, it's wasted time. While you may see the full architecture, most developers won't, they'll only know their own scope. That's why communication between teams is critical, and each team must be able to work independently.

Here is an example of the different teams on the project and their interaction point, I believe that it is important to create such a diagram when designing a system that is being developed by multiple teams. It helps both the team managers and the designers to understand the responsibilities of each team and where development might get stuck:

Figure 13 - Team Responsibilities Diagram

How I Design

Chapter 5

Sections:

- *My Design Approach*
- *Sayings*

Overview:

This chapter shows a more personal perspective of how to how I approach designing a system and what works best for me.

My Design Approach

Here is how I like to approach designing a system:

1. **Decrypt the requirements.** Break the requirements into: The general ideas of the system - What does it do without context, what type of a system is it? The specific contextual requirements - What is unique in this system and what should we put emphasis on? Domain background - Understand the field to uncover core constraints and future evolution paths. Likely future changes - What is probable to change and evolve in the future? What must be flexible (We can't make realistically the whole system flexible. So, we must plan what are our priorities in terms of flexibility). And personal notes - Capture important thoughts and ideas you don't want to forget.
2. **Divide the system into high level components.** Start from a high-level view of the requirements of the system and break down the system's functionalities into main components.
3. **Identify major flows.** keep in mind the different types of flows. The most important are data flows (Where data is moved and modified) and operation flows (Complex algorithms/logic branching from a data flow to enable certain modifications to the data)
4. **Follow flows from start to finish** (or in reverse). At each step, think carefully about the fundamental operations involved and how responsibilities can be split. This naturally enforces the Single Responsibility Principle, since you're focusing on one small, logical step at a time, letting the system branch from the core flows.
5. **Integration with external dependencies via abstraction** (DB/API/UI/Cryptographic library). Only integrate external dependencies through isolating abstractions. Never couple your logic to how a specific tool works.

Sayings

When I design a system, I hear many sayings that I have collected from various friends, co-workers and managers echoing in my head. I highly encourage you to listen and to build your own collection of sayings - it is an invaluable resource.

Here are a selected few to take with you if you find them helpful:

- Decode the requirements as they are the bridge between the non-technical customers and your technical language and thinking.
- External services must have abstractions. Never use internally what you cannot control.
- Do not hide where the logic is happening. Helps reducing over engineering and improve readability.
- Identify flows and follow them from the bottom up. The system can look like a tree, start with the main flow and branch out until you create all the leaves.
- Divide into different components with one defined role. Simplicity is key, and what is simpler than a robot doing one and only one job?

I would like to say thank you for all the people I have taken inspiration from and hear their voices in my head when I design.

How Design Affects Code Quality

Chapter 6

Sections:

- *Clean Code*
- *Refactoring*

Overview:

This chapter examines how design affect the quality of the system's code and how design leads to pain free refactoring.

Clean Code

A slight diversion from the scope of this paper, but this is an area worth exploring. No design can hide or fix fundamentally bad code - but it can contain its impact. By isolating poorly written sections, enforcing meaningful naming for exposed classes and methods, and breaking tangled logic into smaller, more readable parts, design makes the codebase easier to navigate and understand. Good design also influences how developers write code. When class methods are clearly named and have small, well-defined scopes, it becomes much easier to catch errors/bad code during code reviews - before they ever reach production. Developers are less likely to use ambiguous names like `x` when the surrounding function is called “`passCreditCardToSlackingService`” because where does `x` fit in? Spoiler: it's not. In this sense, design doesn't just shape the system structure - it also shapes developer behaviour. It promotes consistency, reduces the chance of errors, and enforces a clean and understandable API between components. Over time, this leads to a higher quality, more maintainable codebase.

Figure 14 - Clean Code Summary

Refactoring

Refactoring is the process of improving the structure and internal quality of code without changing its behaviour. It plays a key role in keeping a system adaptable over time, making the codebase easier to understand, modify, and extend. The ability to refactor confidently is closely tied to the system's design. When coupling is minimized and responsibilities are clear, changes remain localized and predictable, reducing the risk of unintended side effects. For refactoring we must have a solid suite of tests that quickly reveal when something no longer behaves as it should. Without that feedback, even small changes can become risky and introduce bugs. Done well, refactoring not only improves maintainability but often uncovers performance issues and streamlines execution.

A good design doesn't eliminate the need for refactoring - it makes it an easy, not scary, and routine part of development.

When writing a book or paper, we sometimes want to rewrite a section, perhaps to improve clarity or fix inaccuracies. If the work is well structured, it's as simple as finding the relevant section and making the change. But if the information is scattered, repeated in multiple places, and intertwined with other sections that reference it, even changing a single sentence becomes risky. You might break the flow, create contradictions, or leave outdated information lurking in a distant chapter you forgot to update.

Established Design Methodologies

Chapter 7

Sections:

- *Domain Driven Design*
- *Event Sourcing*

Overview:

This chapter explores interesting context dependent methodologies that exist in the world.

Domain Driven Design

Domain Driven Design (DDD) is a software design approach that prioritizes alignment between the domain and the system's architecture. The system is built from a deep understanding of the domain and its core assumptions, guiding how the system should be designed.

It promotes close collaboration with domain experts through a shared language that bridges domain and software design concepts. This improves communication, reduces misunderstandings, and ensures the system reflects the business as it works. You start by identifying key concepts and behaviours in the domain, grouping them into logical components with clear boundaries. The design centres around these components, with business logic at the core and technical details like entities and APIs built around it to serve that logic. DDD isn't about elegance for its own sake - it's about creating a system that fits the problem space exactly, even when that means compromising on software design good practice like expandability or single responsibility.

Yesterday, my grandfather asked me to help fix his laptop screen. He had accidentally switched to a high contrast theme. Over a phone call, we fixed it together - not using my usual method of keyboard shortcuts and quick search, but in a way that made sense for him. We looked for the settings icon on the desktop, opened it, and slowly navigated to the accessibility settings to reset the contrast. It wasn't the fastest or most elegant way, but it was the clearest for him to follow. That's what Domain Driven Design is about: working in the language and approach of the domain, not just the one that's most efficient for the designer.

It's especially useful in complex domains like finance, healthcare, and logistics - Domains where business complexity drives system behaviour. The result is software that's clearer, more adaptable, and better aligned with what matters most: the domain.

So let's see it in action, shall we?

We're building a complete patient treatment system. Our goal is to align it as closely as possible with the real-life steps a patient goes through. This makes it easier for doctors to understand what has happened and what's coming next. It ensures they can quickly find the relevant data for each stage, maintain their familiar workflow, and interact effectively with other doctors and systems.

It starts with scheduling an appointment. The doctor can then refer the patient to a specialist or create a treatment plan. Once the plan is in place, the patient visits the pharmacist to receive medication based on the prescription. At the end of the treatment plan, the patient returns for a follow-up.

Since the doctor may not remember every patient, having a complete medical history, including treatments and data, is crucial for informed decision-making.

Figure 15- Medical System Class Diagram

We didn't begin by designing a software system. We started by describing the real-life process and rules and then aligned them with the software design principles for creating a system.

Event Sourcing

Event sourcing is a pattern where data is stored as a series of recorded events rather than just the current state. Instead of saving the latest snapshot, the system records every change as an event. This allows for reconstructing the current state by replaying the event history.

It's commonly used in systems where accurate historical records are critical, such as in finance or healthcare. It also aids debugging, as every user action can be traced through the event log.

Important aspect to consider when designing event sourcing system are side effects. They must be carefully abstracted away from the core event stream. Replaying events to rebuild state should be a pure operation, free of external consequences like sending emails or making API calls. These side effects should be triggered by separate handlers or listeners, ensuring that the event log remains deterministic and safe to replay. This separation improves modularity, testability, and system resilience.

However, event sourcing has drawbacks. Rebuilding state can be slow if there are many events, and refactoring is challenging - changes to the state flow can break compatibility with older events.

Figure 16 - Event Sourcing Summary

Think of event sourcing like car navigation with a dashcam that records every turn you make. Directions are a sequence of actions: “Turn left here, turn right at the lights, go straight until you see the shop.” If you make a wrong turn, you can replay the recording to return to the point before the mistake. Sometimes different routes lead to the same place, but with the dashcam, you can see exactly how you got there, not just the destination. In event sourcing, we record every “event” so we can rebuild the current state or analyse the full journey by replaying them in order.

Many systems that are built on event sourcing look similar. We always need an event abstraction that holds a common data for all events. A state which the event modifies. A place to store all the events, sometimes even snapshot creator that stores the current state, so it won't need to be rebuilt. And a state builder that builds state based on a series of events.

Here we have designed a bank management system:

Figure 17 - Bank Management System Class Diagram

Clues Within Design

Chapter 8

Sections:

- *Design Smells*

Overview:

This chapter overviews clues about the quality of our design that reveal themselves while we are designing.

Design Smells

Design smells are the way we spot deep and fundamental flaws in our design - things that technically work but feel off, harder to change, understand, or maintain. They show up when something in the structure isn't clean. We should take time every now and then to reflect on our design and see if any smells pop up, especially during design reviews. The smells might look completely different each time, but they usually come from the same broken ideas underneath.

These are some of the top design smells I think you should care about, divided into 3 categories - General, Abstraction related, and ease of change related:

General

1. **God class.** A class with too many responsibilities. It can look as a class with many methods, or an implementation that is too long (A file should consist up to 100/200 lines of code. Depends on your language of choice and the class responsibility).
2. **Vague naming.** A class or component with a vague name like “Manager” or “Handler” makes it easy to violate single responsibility and attracts unwanted logic.
3. **Low cohesion.** Can you describe your class or component in one sentence? No? So, it is a design smell because it means that not all methods share the same purpose, they do not belong together and do not work for the same cause.
4. **High coupling.** The components are too heavily tied and depends on each other. It is easy to spot in the class diagram when you see a lot of arrows between classes.
5. **Duplication of design patterns.** No, I don't necessarily mean design patterns as you know it. I mean multiple similar logic or structure of classes across different components. Duplication of logic.
6. **Coupling between layers.** for example, a UI module accessing the database or processing component directly – creates unnecessary and harmful dependencies across the system. To spot this, ensure a clear separation between modules in your diagram. Then look at the dependency lines; they should only represent what's essential and go through proper abstractions.
7. **Need to expose internal methods or fields.** When a class exposes many of its internal details just to support another class (in C++, this often shows up as one class that needs to be a friend of another), it's a strong sign that something is wrong with the design. This breaks encapsulation and creates tight coupling. It usually means the responsibilities between classes aren't well defined, and you should reconsider how this group of classes is structured.

Abstraction

1. **Complex abstraction.** An abstraction that does not hide internal implementation details is hard to expand and implement in a different way that was firstly implemented.
2. **Duplication.** Multiple abstractions doing the same thing but a bit differently. It is connected to the complex abstraction discussed earlier; it is a flag that your abstractions depend too much on implementation details.
3. **Incomplete abstraction.** If the user needs to know the specific implementation type and the abstraction is not enough, there is no practical use for the abstraction, and the part should get a redesign.
4. **Wrong abstraction.** If two classes share the same function signature, should it be abstracted? Not necessarily. It should have an abstraction only if the abstraction makes sense and the relation between the classes also make sense. Not all shared functions need to have an abstraction, only if the abstraction had a purpose.
5. **Misplaced abstraction.** Remember when I talked about a module like the UI accessing logic from another module directly? I said it must be accessed through an abstraction. But if I place the abstraction inside the UI, that's a misplaced abstraction - parts of the UI module would then contain logic that belongs to a different module.
6. **Too much abstraction.** When you over-abstract everything. Breaking the logic into tiny parts, with each class doing a single thing and every step hidden behind an abstraction - the real implementation ends up scattered across the codebase. It becomes a nightmare to debug and understand, as you constantly jump between layers just to piece together what's going on.

Ease of Change

1. **Shotgun.** Yes, just like the gun. If for a single target, we need to spray our changes across multiple components and files it is hard and dangerous to change. It means logic is scattered across many different parts of the system.
2. **Composition of concrete classes.** When you compose a class using concrete implementations instead of abstractions, you tie your design to specific behaviours. This limits flexibility and makes changes more invasive - altering logic often requires swapping entire classes or rewriting consumers. It breaks the Dependency Inversion Principle and makes future extensions harder.
3. **Territory bypass.** When changes in one area (like business logic) force edits in distant parts of the system (like UI or storage), it signals a breach in module boundaries. This often happens due to leaky abstractions or poor encapsulation. It increases the risk of cascading changes and breaks modularity - e.g., adding a new domain rule shouldn't force you to alter presentation logic.
4. **Hidden dependencies.** When a class depends on things not declared in its constructor or interface - like global state, service locators, or internal instantiations - it becomes unpredictable and harder to reason about. You lose clarity about what the class needs to function, making changes fragile and error prone. Hidden dependencies obscure the real structure of your design.

Figure 18 - Design Smells Summary

Here is a riddle, how many design smells (And which ones) appear in the next diagram?

Figure 19 - Design Smells Riddle

The answers:

1. God Class: “StoreManager” has too many responsibilities.
2. Vague Naming: “MisplacedUIAbstraction” doesn't clearly indicate its purpose.
3. Low Cohesion: “CustomerInteraction” includes unrelated functionalities - it both handles’ queries and feedback.
4. High Coupling: “StoreManager” is heavily dependent on numerous classes.
5. Composition of Concrete Classes: “ReportGenerator” uses concrete classes “JSONReportGenerator” and “XMLReportGenerator” directly.
6. Misplaced Abstraction: “MisplacedUIAbstraction” is accessing logic from different layers directly.

Total design smells count: **6**

Well done!

Emerging Tools

Chapter 9

Sections:

- *AI in Software Design*

Overview:

This chapter overviews emerging trends and their impact on software design.

AI in Software Design

This section explores how AI's approach to software design differs from that of humans, why these differences matter, and what to keep in mind when using AI as a design tool.

AI does not think like humans and lacks the deep, abstract reasoning that humans have. It lacks the understating of what the software design principles are all about, it does not understand abstract concepts as well as humans do. It follows patterns and rules without internalizing the deeper “why” behind them. Much of this paper focuses on what our tools and principles truly represent, and how to design systems with a genuine grasp of the forces that shape them. Designing requires more than applying fixed rules like “If X, then Y.” It demands consideration of multiple dimensions - the business context, the system's long-term future, requirements, what teams are developing this system and what are their expertise, development timelines, existing infrastructure, and more.

Humans integrate such considerations both consciously and subconsciously. When crossing a street, for example, we check traffic lights, scan for vehicles, notice cyclists, and even feel that something is wrong if both the pedestrian's and cars' light is green at the same time. In system design, the list of relevant signals is far longer, more complex, and more abstract - yet we still develop an intuitive “eye” for what feels right or wrong. AI still lacks this intuition. While it can mimic understanding, it does not possess the human-like abstraction thinking and adaptive reasoning needed to make complex, context dependent connections. Research by Martha Lewis and Melanie Mitchell¹ supports this, showing that large language models often lack robust abstract reasoning, particularly outside their training data: “These models in many cases lack the robustness of zero-shot human analogy-making... While they may have some capability for abstract reasoning, LLMs often lack general, robust reasoning abilities.” (Mitchell, 2023).

AI models today have large context width that can maintain and process large texts and long conversations. But those models are also prone to hallucinations and context losing, especially when you reach near the limit of the context window. Those phenomena are dangerous if the model has access to the main system diagram/design documentation as it can break the correctness of the design or rely on non existing

¹ M. Lewis and M. Mitchell, "Evaluating the Robustness of Analogical Reasoning in GPT Models", OpenReview, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=t5cy5v9wph>

services. And while a human designer has an evolving understanding of the design process and the decisions made and why they were made. AI doesn't, and when it starts to hallucinate or forget it sometimes must be restarted and start its understanding from scratch - Like a new team member, but if the AI takes the place of the designer and the human designer is not an expert on the system, who will teach the context to the model?

The design of a system will never be perfectly aligned to the general good practices and principles, and it's fine. When designing we consider trade offs quite often, and that's a challenge we tackle by understanding what the trade off implications will be, are they aligned to the priorities of the system and what can be done to minimize their effect on the system quality. AI does not have the deeper understanding of the principles and has a harder time prioritizing them for the exact context, just like AI does not have morals - It knows when something is wrong or right by the book, but should a man get a ticket for speeding while taking his wife in labour to the hospital? The grey areas are where the AI struggles most.

AI today is a tool. You ask, it answers. You give it a task, it executes. It tends to agree with your view even when you're wrong. If you ask AI to design a system using microservices, it will do exactly that. Unlike a human colleague who questions your choices and challenges your assumptions, AI rarely does so. It only flags problems when it hits a major obstacle, which is often too late. Those human challenges often spark conversations that expose gaps in thinking or knowledge and improve understanding of requirements and rationale - conversations AI skips entirely.

However, AI excels at exploring alternatives. It can generate multiple complete system designs in the time it takes a human to create one and run simulations to identify the most efficient. When assisting humans, AI can instantly generate and tweak architectural diagrams, speeding up experimentation and visualization.

One interesting organizational use of LLMs is to embed architectural knowledge into an accessible AI expert. When a system's architecture is defined, developers and business stakeholders can query the AI for consistent, contextual architectural guidance - spreading knowledge and freeing designers from repetitive explanations.

AI is trained on vast amounts of data and has seen more systems than any human could in a lifetime. AI models help eliminate knowledge gaps even the most senior designers have and can propose solutions the designer didn't know existed. This enables solving complex problems more effectively and often in better ways. These models are experts across disciplines - from science to literature to generated art and photos. That helps AI tackle architecture in systems that are related to specific domains, as it has the broad understanding of the business side, the software development knowledge, the software design principles and the domain knowledge. It can take into consideration all aspects of the system.

AI is a great way to bring awareness of the importance of design to developers by making designing capabilities accessible to every developer. Having seen many systems, AI can easily generate simple or common designs correctly. For developers without prior intentional design experience, this can be a game changer - helping them avoid future problems, enhance system robustness, and prepare for future versions and changes. Success using AI-assisted design can encourage developers to adopt design practices and appreciate their value, even when it adds complexity.

Letting AI design systems from scratch isn't ideal yet, but AI can contribute significantly with minimal human guidance. AI excels at pattern recognition, making it a strong evaluator of designs - detecting failure points, logic duplication, separation violations, and other design smells. Because AI treats principles like rules, it effectively spots deviations from best practices and alerts human designers, who can then assess whether the deviation is necessary or if a better design exists.

Much of today's system design work involve relatively small extensions that are built upon large infrastructure like adding a functionality of AI chat that uses the context of open browser tabs. In this sense, will AI be able to handle it alone? Mostly yes. Those extensions are smaller and simpler than designing a large and complex infrastructure from scratch. While lacking deep thinking skills and having some difficulties in different aspects of design, it can produce decent results, especially when serving as a partner to a human architect.

By its nature, AI doesn't produce groundbreaking results. It recombines past data in ways that may seem creative and solves existing problems better, but it fails to generate extraordinary outcomes based on completely new approaches. In domains where AI lacks data or at the cutting edge of technological innovation, its contribution is limited. The main role in driving tomorrow's groundbreaking technology will continue to rely on human insight and creativity.

Design as a Series of Tradeoffs

Chapter 10

Sections:

- *Inside Out or Outside In?*
- *Tradeoffs*

Overview:

This chapter talks about accepting the existence of trade offs and dealing with them effectively.

Inside Out or Outside In?

Inside Out or Outside In? - What do you think about first, how to do something or what do you want it to do? Do you start by defining the abstraction or the implementation? This question confuses many developers and designers and is very similar to the TDD (Test Driven Development) vs implementation first debate.

On one hand, you want to define the behaviour first and therefore the abstraction. But if you don't yet understand the implementation, you risk creating a poor abstraction - one that forces you to pass awkward parameters or break encapsulation later.

My rule of thumb is that you should define behaviour first whenever possible. It reduces coupling and does not make the abstraction (Higher level module) depend, even subconsciously, on the implementation details (Low level module).

But there are exceptions, for performance-critical components, low-level OS interactions, or any part with strong external constraints, start Inside-Out. In these cases, behaviour is dictated by the environment, not by your intentions. You likely don't yet have the necessary knowledge or strategy to abstract it cleanly so first explore, experiment, build a small proof of concept. Then, once you understand the boundaries and limitations, you can shape a responsible abstraction around it.

Tradeoffs

Design, in the end, is a series of trade offs: flexibility versus simplicity, fast development versus a complete, maintainable system, isolation and abstraction versus performance (e.g., more functions mean deeper call stacks and slower performance). You must accept that perfection in all aspects is impossible and set clear priorities. What needs flexibility? What demands top performance? How long should the system last? These answers guide your design far better than any “tool.” You **MUST** use your mind - and isn't that the real fun and challenge?

Closing Remarks

Chapter 11

Sections:

- *Farewell Words*

Overview:

This chapter provides the closing words and how to contact me - The author.

Farewell Words

Software design, as I wrote earlier, has no absolute right or wrong. It demands thought over blind rule-following. That's why I urge you to think critically about everything in this paper and everything you hear about software design. Go beyond the words - understand the reasoning behind them. Shape your own views and approaches. That's how you'll design better systems.

Software design sparks conversation between people with different perspectives and opinions. This paper reflects my current perspective in 2025, at age 19. I am certain it will evolve in the future, and I would like to hear your opinions - both on this paper and on your own view of software design. Feel welcome to reach out via [Email](#) or on [LinkedIn](#).

On a more personal note, my journey with software design began with failures. I tried to create several large-scale personal projects on my own and failed for various reasons - reasons that would not have existed if I had known how to design systems at all. I am grateful for those failures, as they opened my mind to learning and made me truly grasp the importance of software design. To fail is a good thing, and design is an iterative process.

Thank you for reading. Take what you've learned, question it, adapt it, and make it your own. Keep thinking deeply, building deliberately, and never stop refining your craft. Before we part ways, I wish you good luck on your journey!

Supplementary Material

Sections:

- *Acknowledgements*
- *Table of Figures*
- *References and Additional Reading*
- *Appendices*
 - o *Technical Glossary*

Overview:

Holds additional content complementing the main chapters: acknowledgments, appendices, and references.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank everyone who assisted me during the writing of this paper - for their phrasing suggestions, constructive criticism, encouragement to provide more examples and analogies, and guidance in clarifying ideas and strengthening sections. I would especially like to thank two people:

- [Tony Patti](#) - For showing me first-hand the process of writing a technical paper, for his prior papers which helped me refine the structure and phrasing of this paper, and for his thoughtful tips and perspectives that encouraged me to approach several sections from new angles. Tony also pushed me to add more information and even a full additional chapter. His support and encouragement throughout the process meant a great deal to me.
- [Arad Cohen](#) - For exposing me to efficient ways of reaching readers and conveying technical knowledge clearly. Arad encouraged me to use real-life analogies to make concepts more relatable and introduced me to websites for creating clearer, more visually appealing diagrams, which inspired me to explore even better tools on my own. His guidance was invaluable in helping me communicate the ideas in this paper more clearly and engagingly.

Table of Figures

All summaries in this document were generated with *Microsoft Copilot*, based on the section content.

Figure 1 - Dependencies Summary.....	10
Figure 2 - Bad Newsroom Class Diagram.....	11
Figure 3 - Good Newsroom Class Diagram.....	12
Figure 4 - Library Class Diagram.....	14
Figure 5 - Secured Resource Access System Class Diagram.....	16
Figure 6 - Straightforward Resource Access System Class Diagram.....	17
Figure 7 - Design For Seucrity Summary.....	18
Figure 8 - Single/Multi Apartment Class Diagram.....	20
Figure 9 - Design for Change Summary.....	21
Figure 10 - Smart Farm Management System Class Diagram.....	24
Figure 11 - Inconsistent File Tree.....	29
Figure 12 - Communication Summary.....	31
Figure 13 - Team Responsibilities Diagram.....	32
Figure 14 - Clean Code Summary.....	38
Figure 15- Medical System Class Diagram.....	43
Figure 16 - Event Sourcing Summary.....	46
Figure 17 - Bank Managment System Class Diagram.....	47
Figure 18 - Design Smells Summary.....	51
Figure 19 - Design Smells Riddle.....	52

References and Additional Reading

- M. Lewis and M. Mitchell, “Evaluating the Robustness of Analogical Reasoning in GPT Models”, *OpenReview*, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=t5cy5v9wph>
- S. Goedecke, “Everything I know about good system design”, seangoedecke.com, 2025, [Online]. Available: <https://www.seangoedecke.com/good-system-design/>

Appendices

Appendix A: Technical Glossary

- **SOLID**: A set of five very popular design principles.
- **SRP (Single Responsibility Principle)**: A class should have only one reason to change. Keeps code modular and focused.
- **OCP (Open Closed Principle)**: Modules should be open for extension but closed for modification. Encourages extending behaviour without rewriting existing code.
- **LSP (Liskov Substitution Principle)**: Subclasses should be usable in place of their base classes without affecting correctness. Or how I like to call it: Just define your abstractions right.
- **ISP (Interface Segregation Principle)**: Prefer many specific interfaces over one general-purpose interface. Prevents forcing components to depend on unused methods.
- **DIP (Dependency Inversion Principle)**: High-level modules should not depend on low-level modules. Both should depend on abstractions.
- **DRY - Don't Repeat Yourself**: Avoid duplication by abstracting repeated logic or knowledge into one place.
- **IoC**: Inversion of Control. Extracting the control of the dependencies to an external service that passes the dependencies from the outside using DI or Events. The class does not manage its dependencies, something else does.
- **DI - Dependency Injection**: A technique for supplying dependencies from the outside, making modules loosely coupled and easier to test. Pass objects that fit a certain abstraction in the function arguments/constructor.
- **Design Pattern**: General reusable solutions to common design problems, such as Factory, Strategy, Observer, etc.
- **UML - Unified Modelling Language**: A visual language for specifying, constructing, and documenting software design using diagrams.
- **Monolith**: An architecture where the entire system is built as a single unit, often leading to harder scalability.
- **Microservices**: An architecture pattern where a system is built as a collection of small, loosely coupled services. Allows independent scaling and deployment.
- **N-Tier Architecture**: A layered architecture that separates presentation, logic, and data access. Promotes separation of concerns.

- **3-Tier architecture:** Divide the system into 3 components – UI (User Interface), BL (Business Logic) and DAL (Data Abstraction Layer).
- **Hexagonal Architecture:** Also called Ports and Adapters. Separates the core logic from the outside world via interfaces, allowing greater testability and flexibility.
- **Cohesion:** Measures how closely-related the responsibilities of a module are. High cohesion is desirable.
- **Coupling:** Degree of interdependence between modules. Low coupling makes systems easier to change and test.
- **Least Privilege:** A security principle ensuring each module has only the minimum access it needs.
- **Audit Logging:** Capturing logs of system activities for debugging, monitoring, and security.
- **TDD - Test Driven Development:** Write tests before writing the code. Define behaviour before implementation details.
- **Factory:** A design pattern that encapsulates object creation logic.
- **Interface:** An abstraction that defines behaviour, allowing different implementations without changing calling code.
- **Base class:** An abstract class that defines basic behaviour for reducing code repeating.